

Abstract

Conventional and Acupuncture Treatments for Chemotherapy-Induced Peripheral Neuropathic Pain: A Comprehensive Review.

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Abstract

Background: Chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy (CIPN) is a debilitating clinical condition arising from the neurotoxicity of specific chemotherapeutic agents. It primarily affects the peripheral nervous system, with the severity of symptoms typically dependent on the type of drug administered, the duration of treatment, and the cumulative dosage. In some instances, nerve damage may be further exacerbated by the underlying malignancy itself.

Clinical Context: The pharmacological agents most frequently associated with CIPN include vinca alkaloids (vincristine, vinblastine), taxanes (paclitaxel, docetaxel), platinum-based compounds (cisplatin, carboplatin, and oxaliplatin), bortezomib, epothilones (ixabepilone), and thalidomide along with its analogues. The concurrent use of two or more of these neurotoxic agents significantly increases the risk of developing severe sensory or motor deficits. To date, conventional medical interventions that are effective for general peripheral neuropathies have largely proven inadequate for the specific management of CIPN.

Objective: Despite significant advancements in understanding the cellular mechanisms of neuronal toxicity, effective preventative strategies remain elusive. Consequently, the management of established CIPN remains predominantly symptomatic. Conversely, a growing body of research suggests that acupuncture is a safe and effective modality for alleviating cancer-related symptoms and various forms of peripheral neuropathy. This review aims to evaluate the efficacy of acupuncture as a specialised intervention for CIPN.

Methods: The evaluation of acupuncture's therapeutic potential in this review focuses on clinical trials that utilise rigorous control conditions—including standard of care, placebo, sham acupuncture, or no-treatment controls—to provide a balanced comparison against active acupuncture interventions.

Keywords: Acupuncture; Chemotherapy; Chemotherapy-Induced Peripheral Neuropathy; Neuropathic Pain; Oncology; Neurotoxicity.

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